

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF ART PEDAGOGY IN RAISING THE SPIRITUALITY OF YOUNG PEOPLE

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ABSTRACT

Solving the issue of using art as an effective way of self-exploration and creative self-development is one of the important tasks of modern pedagogy. The arts occupy a special place among the leading components of educational strategy. In the conditions of secular general education, art is the only area in which the emotional and moral development of a growing person and his familiarization with the highest spiritual values of his people and humanity can naturally take place. The purpose of this article is to show the need to create an art-pedagogical space as an innovative environment for the creative development and professional training of students of pedagogical universities.

INTRODUCTION

Changes are being observed in the Uzbek education system, representing the next stage in the formation of a new school. That is why significant changes are taking place in the approach to the pedagogical theory and practice of the educational process: new content, new approaches, new rights, relationships and types of behavior, as well as a new pedagogical mentality are brought to the fore.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Even in ancient times, the great thinkers Aristotle, Democritus, Pythagoras, Plato defined art as the source of the formation of harmony and order not only in the entire universe, but also in the human soul. Komensky Y.A., Pestalozzi I.G., Sukhomlinsky V.A., Tolstoy L.N., Ushinsky K.D., Shatsky S.T. wrote about the pedagogical possibilities of art in their works. and others [1-8].

The arts occupy a special place among the leading components of educational strategy. Art is used in the educational process primarily in the direction of the emotional sphere of the individual; it enriches a person not only with knowledge, but also with thoughts, feelings and experiences; it offers aesthetic pleasure and cultivates aesthetic taste. In terms of its content, art has a positive impact on the formation of personality: it enriches cognitive activity, develops a person's perception abilities, expands his spiritual world, forms attitudes and

assessments not only to works of art, but also to the wider world, to people and to human relationships [2].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The essence of art pedagogy is the integration of art, pedagogy, psychology for education, training, development, and support of a growing personality. At the same time, art becomes a kind of mediator that provides psychological conditions for perception, comprehension, and consolidation of pedagogical content.

The tasks and functions of art pedagogy differ significantly from existing art education programs in that its goal is not to teach a child, for example, to draw, but to develop the ability for self-expression, self-knowledge, and the acquisition of communication skills. Art pedagogy helps the study of art, knowledge of its history and theory, mastery of practical skills in organizing communication: artistic perception and experience of works of art, practical skills in using the powerful educational and aesthetic development potential of art, practical skills in artistic and creative activity, and research skills.

Art pedagogy helps develop children's imagination, attention, creative thinking, the ability to freely express their feelings and moods, and work in a team.

Therefore, the subject field of art-pedagogical influence is, first of all, the sensory-emotional sphere of the individual: the processes of perception and sensations, attention and mnemonic memory, reflexive abilities and emotional-volitional regulation, non-verbal-communicative culture [4].

In the study of art pedagogy as a science, the scientific works of Sergeeva N.Yu. are of interest, in which the formulation and justification for the introduction into scientific use of the concept of "art pedagogy" as "a modern direction of pedagogical science that studies patterns, mechanisms, principles, rules for the inclusion of means" are given art into the educational context to solve professional and pedagogical problems" [5]. According to Sergeeva N.Yu. "The subject of art pedagogy in general can be defined as the development of a person through the means of art and artistic activity in the educational space. The tasks of art pedagogy as a separate independent direction of pedagogical science include:

6) A comprehensive description and interpretation of the mechanisms of the influence of art and artistic activity on a person in the educational space.

7) Study of the pedagogical potential of certain types, directions, genres of art and artistic activity.

8) Development of theoretical foundations for organizing the pedagogical process using art and artistic activity.

9) Designing the content of art-pedagogical activities.

10) Development of methods and technologies for the variable use of art and artistic activities in the educational process."

Particular attention in the scientific and pedagogical literature on art pedagogy in modern universities is paid to art-pedagogical support for the professional training of students at pedagogical universities. It is the creation of an art environment that is currently the most important condition for the development of the pedagogical position of every future teacher. The art environment is defined "as a combination of the following environments:

a) a cultural environment for learning and teaching, formed with the help of culture-intensive technologies and a variety of high-quality means of various disciplines of the humanities and natural sciences, as well as cultural components of the content of all educational courses;

b) the cultural environment of one's own active learning activities;

c) multicultural educational space in an educational institution; d) cultural mass media environment of self-education;

d) cultural environment of communication between children and adults; f) cultural environment of the family;

e) cultural environment of children's and teenagers' amateur activities;

f) the cultural environment of additional education and the cultural environment of personal self-development zones (as an internal cultural space)."

CONCLUSION

Education must ensure the formation of a new culture. That is why in educational theory and practice the formation of professional education and the pedagogical position of a teacher is of particular relevance, since both the psychological comfort of the educational environment he forms and the effectiveness of his professional activities in general depend on his views, beliefs, and attitudes.

The process of a future teacher's entry into art should be carried out on the basis of the formation of his aesthetic taste as an attitude towards the quality of the work, its content and form, which historically gravitates towards the classics. Aesthetic taste as a core component of aesthetic consciousness develops on the basis of aesthetic experience, in which communication with the best examples of culture and art occupies a significant place. Art pedagogy has rich potential for successfully solving the problems of art education.

Education is a vital organ of culture, on the work of which the very existence of culture in general and artistic culture in particular depends. The practice of training students in pedagogical universities has shown the need to organize the educational process from the standpoint of alternative pedagogy, innovative approaches to the organization of educational and developmental space. The creation of an art environment at a university is currently the most important condition for the development of the pedagogical position of every future teacher.

References:

1. Anisimov V.P., Smetanina A.Yu. Art-pedagogical support for spiritual and moral development of the individual. Tver, 2018. 280 p.
2. Anisimov V.P. Art pedagogy as a system of psychological support of the educational process // Bulletin of the Orenburg State University. university. 2013. No. 4. pp. 146-148.
3. Balagazova S.T. The role of art in the formation of a creative personality // Pedagogy. 2015. No. 5. P. 70-72.
4. Bulatova O.S. Art-pedagogical approach in education. Tyumen, 2014. 230 p.

5. Verkhovodova R.A., Galustov R.A. Foreign experience. Art pedagogy as a system of integrative application of art elements in the educational process // Bulletin of the Adygea State University. Series: Pedagogy and psychology. 2011. No. 1. pp. 15-17.
6. Kodzhaspirova G.M., Kodzhaspirov A.Yu. Dictionary of pedagogy. M., 2015. P. 155.
7. Melik-Pashaev A.A. About the state and possibilities of art education. Analytic note. URL: <http://art-inschool.ru>
8. Pechko L.P. General and aesthetic culture in education and personal development // Culture, experience, imagination of a developing personality in art education: Collection of scientific papers and materials of a scientific-practical conference. M., 2018. Issue 2. pp. 18-26.